

Digital language and communication training for EU scientists

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Protocol: Focus group study

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Note: Focus groups are **best run in-person**.

The purpose of a focus group study is to confirm previously identified trends or results of analysis (from surveys, interviews), and to gain a **more in-depth understanding about the needs of the target audience based on their expressed opinions and attitudes, facial expressions/body language, etc.** The focus group moderator facilitates an exchange of viewpoints and/or disagreements between participants with different profiles (e.g., researchers and/or university administrators).

To encourage participation, 2-5 people should be invited. They should not have previously been interviewed for this project.

Duration: Around 45-60 minutes.

Number of focus groups: 1 per partner (6 total).

Equipment: A good quality video-audio recording tool is necessary to capture both image and voice.

Warm-up and introductions	Set the tone	Thanks for attending this focus group about X. I am sure this is a busy time for everyone and so I really appreciate your being here today. My name is [...] and I'm working on the DILAN project (Digital Language and Communication Training for EU Scientists). I'll say more about the project in just a moment.
	Break the ice	First, I'd like to start off by having everyone introduce themselves. Could you please tell us your name and a bit about yourself in your current position here at [institution name].
	State end goal of research to help participants start focusing their thoughts	What we want to do today is talk about the STEMM scientists' digital communication practices.

		<p>The results will be used to create training resources for the digital communication of science.</p> <p>You were invited because of your involvement in [...]</p>
	<p>Set ground rules (explicitly allow disagreement, mention that you are videotaping or recording, inform participants about rights)</p>	<p>Before we begin, here are a few ground rules.</p> <p>There are no wrong answers here, so please feel free to share your point of view even if it differs from what others have said. Keep in mind that I am/we are just as interested in negative comments as positive comments. At times the negative comments are the most helpful.</p> <p>Please keep in mind that I'll be recording the session: people often say helpful things but I can't write fast enough to note them all down. Also, although we may be on a first name basis today, your names will not be used in our reports. You may be assured of complete confidentiality.</p> <p>[The participants should be given the information sheet and asked to sign the consent form at this point]</p> <p>My role as moderator will be to guide the discussion as you talk with each other. With that said, let's begin.</p>
<p>Topic 1. Practices for sharing research results (publication language and audience)</p>	<p>Introduction to Topic 1: Right, so to start things off, I'd like to talk about sharing the results of scientific research, both in terms of publication language and making science accessible to a wider non-specialist audience.</p>	
	<p>University administration-oriented questions</p>	<p>Researcher-oriented questions</p>
	<p>How does your institution support science dissemination?</p> <p>What have you, or others at your institution, done to encourage research communication in English?</p>	<p>Do you know how your institution supports science dissemination?</p> <p>Does your institution support you to publish in English?</p> <p>Suppose you were in charge and could make changes that would improve support for research</p>

	<p>How does your institution feel about outreach to a wider audience? Some examples might include: encouraging Citizen Science projects, bringing scientists and non-scientist audiences together through activities like speed-searching (like speed-dating). Why is that?</p>	<p>communication in English at your institution? What would you do?</p> <p>How and when do you think researchers should engage in outreach to a wider, non-specialist audience?</p>
	<p>Phrases for engaging specific individuals:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • So [xxx], can we turn to you now? Do you have any ideas why...? • I'd like to ask X to tell us about ... • Any comments on that point?
	<p>Phrases for taking the discussion further:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • So what you're saying is... • If I understand correctly... • What do you mean when you say "X"? • Can you give us a few examples? • Can you say anything else about that? • Can you build on the point [Name] just made?
	<p>Phrases for ending the topic</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before we move on, is there anything we didn't touch on that you feel is important? • Are there any other points you'd like to make about this subject before we move on? • Would you like to say anything else about X? • Do you think there are related topics we should have covered, but didn't? • Alright then, let's move on to the next point, shall we? • If no one has anything else to add, let's continue on to the next topic.
<p>Topic 2. Perceptions of new forms of</p>	<p>Introduction to Topic 2: Great. So, the second topic I would like to discuss concerns new forms of science communication. As you know, today there are many new digital forms and media for communicating research, such as video and graphical abstracts, blogs, podcasts or videocasts, infographic posters, etc.</p>	

communicating science	University administration-oriented questions	Researcher-oriented questions
	<p>Have you or colleagues at your institution provided opportunities for researchers at your institution to learn these new forms and media? (see examples in Intro to Topic 2)</p> <p>In our survey, we found that most researchers are interested in these new digital forms but don't actually use them. What do you think might help researchers use them more often?</p>	<p>How and when do you use them?</p> <p>Could you tell us about any positive experiences with...</p> <p>Could you tell us about any disappointments with...</p>
	<p>Phrases for engaging specific individuals:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • So [xxx], can we turn to you now? Do you have any ideas why...? • I'd like to ask X to tell us about ... • Any comments on that point?
	<p>Phrases for taking the discussion further:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • So what you're saying is... • If I understand correctly... • What do you mean when you say "X"? • Can you give us a few examples? • Can you say anything else about that? • Can you build on the point [Name] just made?
	<p>Phrases for ending the topic</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before we move on, is there anything we didn't touch on that you feel is important? • Are there any other points you'd like to make about this subject before we move on? • Would you like to say anything else about X? • Do you think there are related topics we should have covered, but didn't? • Alright then, let's move on to the next point, shall we? • If no one has anything else to add, let's continue on to the next topic.

Topic 3. Identifying learning and training needs	Introduction to Topic 3: Ok, so the last topic I'd like to explore with you is whether you see any training needs in digital science communication for researchers at your institution.	
	University administration-oriented questions	Researcher-oriented questions
	<p>If you were to set up a program or initiative to better support researchers' digital scientific communication needs, what would you focus on?</p> <p>Amongst the following options, which do you think needs the most attention at your institution?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicating science to a wider audience • Communicating science in English • Helping scientists use new digital forms (videos, blogs....) to communicate science 	<p>If you could design a program to support your and your colleagues' digital scientific communication, what would you target?</p> <p>Amongst the following options, which do you feel researchers need the most help with?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicating science to a wider audience • Communicating science in English • Using new digital forms (videos, blogs....) to communicate science <p>Of all the things we've spoken about, what is most important to you?</p>
	Phrases for engaging specific individuals:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • So [xxx], can we turn to you now? Do you have any ideas why...? • I'd like to ask X to tell us about ... • Any comments on that point?
	Phrases for taking the discussion further:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • So what you're saying is... • If I understand correctly... • What do you mean when you say "X"? • Can you give us a few examples? • Can you say anything else about that? • Can you build on the point [Name] just made?
Phrases for ending the topic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before we move on, is there anything we didn't touch on that you feel is important? • Are there any other points you'd like to make about this subject before we move on? 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Would you like to say anything else about X? • Do you think there are related topics we should have covered, but didn't?
Wrap-up	Summary question	<p>So, to sum up our discussion today [...]. / Right, let's recap what we said today [...].</p> <p>Is this an adequate summary?</p>
	Participants reflect on entire discussion and offer opinions on topics	Of all the things we discussed today, what to you is the most important?
	Moderator reviews study purpose and find question	<p>So, the purpose today was to [...].</p> <p>Have we missed anything? / Is there anything else anyone would like to raise before we finish?</p>
	Close	Thank you all for attending today. Your thoughts are very important for our training program.